

Gender						
Age						
Qualification						
IT experience in a financial institution						
Occupation						
Constructs	Items	SD	D	N	A	SA
1. Physical Security	Please rank, where SD=Strongly Disagree, N=Neutral and SA=Strongly Agree					
	1.1) Security guards monitor people entering and leaving the server room and critical ICT infrastructure sites					
	1.2) The bank uses CCTV, biometrics, swipe cards, electronic locks, alarm systems, bar codes, or related devices to control access to restricted areas and equipment					
	1.3) The bank ICT infrastructure is protected against natural hazards (e.g., lighting, fire, floods, earthquake, etc.)					
	1.4) Computer rooms are locked after work hours					
	1.5) Access to bank hardware infrastructure is restricted					
2. Application Security						
	2.1 The bank utilises anti-phishing solutions to prevent phishing attacks					
	2.2 There is anti-malware software to detect and remove any threats from malicious software					
	2.3 User identification and authentication are required before logging into banking applications					
	2.4 Log files are regularly analysed to detect and prevent threats					
	2.5 Bank Application Software are always kept up-to-date					
3. Data Security						
	3.1 Regular backups for the data and software configuration settings are regularly performed and kept offsite					
	3.2 Data analytics are being used for fraud detection and deterrence					
	3.3 The bank has implemented safety mechanisms (e.g., RAID, replication, data encryption, transaction, rollback) and is able to recover from data loss or corruption within the recommended time					
	3.4 Private information is kept only in an encrypted format					

	3.5 Strong passwords are used to restrict access to bank's data					
4. Network Security						
	4.1) Antivirus software and all security-related software receive regular updates to protect the internal bank network against security breaches					
	4.2) Wireless security products secure the bank's wireless network (e.g., use of strong passwords, wireless intrusion detection, a wireless encryption protocol, Mac address filtering)					
	4.3) Firewalls with intrusion detection software and host auditing software are installed to monitor computers and servers for signs of intrusions					
	4.4) Virtual private networks are used as communication channels between bank systems.					
	4.5) Trusted Certificates are used to encrypt and decrypt packets both at server and client, respectively					
5. Internet Security						
	5.1) A demilitarised zone (DMZ), firewalls' routers, and another Internet access control protects bank systems against threats from an external unsecured network					
	5.2) Digital signatures assure the authority of any electronic documents sent via the Internet (e.g., use of passwords, public-key encryption, private encryption and digital certificates).					
	5.3) Web content filtering and monitoring systems on the server and individual workstations prevent users from accessing inappropriate websites or content					
	5.4) All bank web-based URL always begins with HTTPS://					
	5.5) The bank email systems forbid uploading of potentially harmful software like .exe and .zip files					
6. Identity Theft						
	6.1) Individual bank cards have been illegally used without permission of the cardholder					
	6.2) Unauthorised charges on bank accounts have occurred in some way					
	6.3) Stolen identity had been used to conduct purchases					
	6.4) Others had used personal information to apply for benefits					
	6.5) Money has been deducted from personal accounts without permission					
Which Security framework are you using?		Yes		No		

Do you have the office of the Chief Security Officer?	
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